

NUMERICAL FUNCTIONS AND TRIPLETS

I. Bălăcenoiu, D. Bordea, V. Seleacu

We consider the functions: $f_s, f_d, f_p, F : \mathbf{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbf{N}$, where $f_s(k) = n, f_d(k) = n, f_p(k) = n, F(k) = n$, n being, respectively, the least natural number such that $k/n! - 1, k/n! + 1, k/n! \pm 1, k/n!$ or $k/n! \pm 1$. This functions have the next properties:

1. Obviously, from definition of this function, it results:

$$F(k) = \min\{S(k), f_p(k)\} = \min\{S(k), f_s(k), f_d(k)\}$$

where S is the Smarandache function (see [3]).

2. $F(k) \leq S(k), F(k) \leq f_s(k), F(k) \leq f_d(k), F(k) \leq f_p(k)$
3. $F(k) = S(k)$ if k is even, $k \geq 4$.
Proof. For any $n \in \mathbf{N}, n \geq 2, n!$ is even, $n! \pm 1$ are odd. If k is even, then k cannot divide $n! \pm 1$. So $F(k) = S(k) = n \geq 2$ if k is even, $k \geq 4$.
4. If $p > 3$ is prime number, then $F(p) \leq p - 2$.
Proof. According to Wilson's theorem $(p - 1)! + 1 = M_p$. Because $(p - 2)! - 1 + (p - 1)! + 1 = (p - 2)!p$ results for $p > 3, (p - 2)! - 1 = M_p$ and so $F(p) \leq p - 2$.
5. $F(m!) = F(m! \pm 1) = S(m!) = m$.
6. The equation $F(k) = F(k + 1)$ has infinitely many solutions, because, according to the property 5), there is the solutions $k = m!, m \in \mathbf{N}^*$.

7. If $F(k) = S(k)$ and n is the least natural number such that $k/n!$, then k not divide $s! \pm 1$ for $s < n$.

Let $k = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdot p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}$. According to $S(k) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq r} \{S_{p_i}(\alpha_i)\}$, it results that $S(k) \geq p_h$, where $p_h = \min\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r\}$.

If k not divide $s! \pm 1$ for $s \leq p_h$, then k not divide $t! \pm 1$ for $t > p_h$.

Consequently, if k not divide $(n-1)!$, $k/n!$ and k not divide $s! \pm 1$ for $s \leq \min\{n, p_h\}$, then $F(k) = S(k) = n$.

Obviously, the numbers $k = 3t$, t being odd, $t \neq 1$, have $p_h = 3$ and they satisfy the condition $3t$ not divide $s! \pm 1$ for $s = 1, 2, 3$.

Therefore, for $k = 3t$, t odd, $t \neq 1$, $F(3t) = S(3t) = n$, n being the least natural number such that $3t/n!$.

8. The partition "bai" of the odd numbers.

$$\text{Let } A = \{k \in \mathbf{N} \mid k \text{ odd and } F(k) = S(k)\}$$

$$B = \{k \in \mathbf{N} \mid k \text{ odd and } F(k) < S(k)\}$$

(A, B) is the partition "bai" of the odd numbers.

Into A there are numbers $k = 3t$, t odd, $t \neq 1$. Obviously, A has infinitely many elements.

Into B there are numbers $k = t! \pm 1$ with $t \geq 3$, $t \in \mathbf{N}$. Obviously, B has infinitely many elements.

Definition 1 Let $n \in \mathbf{N}^*$. We called triplet \hat{n} , the set:
 $n-1, n, n+1$.

Definition 2 Let $k < n$. The triplets \hat{k}, \hat{n} are separated if
 $k+1 < n-1$, i.e. $n-k > 2$.

Definition 3 The triplets \hat{k}, \hat{n} are l_s -relatively prime if
 $(k-1, n-1) = 1$, $(k+1, n+1) \neq 1$.

For example: $\hat{6}$ and $\widehat{72}$ are l_s -relatively prime.

Definition 4 The triplets \hat{k}, \hat{n} are l_d -relatively prime if
 $(k-1, n-1) \neq 1$, $(k+1, n+1) = 1$.

Definition 5 The triplets \hat{k}, \hat{n} are l -relatively prime if
 $(k-1, n-1) = 1$, $(k+1, n+1) = 1$.

Definition 6 The triplets \hat{k}, \hat{n} are d -relatively prime if $(k-1, n+1) = 1, (k+1, n-1) = 1$.

For example: $\hat{2}$ and $\hat{6}$ are d -relatively prime.

Definition 7 Let $k < n$. The triplets \hat{k}, \hat{n} are d_s -relatively prime if $(k-1, n+1) = 1, (k+1, n-1) \neq 1$.

For example: $\hat{6}$ and $\widehat{120}$ are d_s -relatively prime.

Definition 8 Let $k < n$. The triplets \hat{k}, \hat{n} are d_d -relatively prime if $(k-1, n+1) \neq 1, (k+1, n-1) = 1$.

Example: $\hat{6}$ and $\widehat{24}$ are d_d -relatively prime.

Definition 9 The triplets \hat{k}, \hat{n} are p -relatively prime if $(k-1, n-1) = 1, (k-1, n+1) = 1, (k+1, n-1) = 1, (k+1, n+1) = 1$.

Obviously, if \hat{k}, \hat{n} are p -relatively prime, then they are l and d -relatively prime.

For example: $\widehat{24}$ and $\widehat{120}$ are p -relatively prime.

Definition 10 Let $k < n$. The triplets \hat{k}, \hat{n} are F -relatively prime if

$$\begin{aligned} (k-1, n-1) = 1, (k+1, n-1) = 1, \\ (k-1, n) = 1, (k+1, n) = 1 \\ (k-1, n+1) = 1, (k+1, n+1) = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 11 The triplets \hat{k}, \hat{n} are t -relatively prime if $(k-1, n-1) \cdot (k-1, n) \cdot (k-1, n+1) \cdot (k, n-1) \cdot (k, n) \cdot (k, n+1) \cdot (k+1, n-1) \cdot (k+1, n) \cdot (k+1, n+1) = 6$.

For example: $\hat{2}$ and $\hat{4}$ are t -relatively prime.

Definition 12 Let $H \subset \mathbb{N}^*$. The triplet $\hat{n}, n \in H$ is, respectively, $l_s, l_d, l, d, d_s, d_d, p, F, t$ -prime concerned at H , if $\forall s \in H, s < n$, the triplets \hat{s}, \hat{n} are, respectively, $l_s, l_d, l, d, d_s, d_d, p, F, t$ -relatively prime.

Let $H = \{n! | n \in \mathbb{N}^*\}$. For the triplets $\hat{m}, m \in H$ there are particular properties.

Proposition 1 Let $k < n$. The triplets $(\widehat{k!}), (\widehat{n!})$ are separated if $n > \max\{2, k\}$.

Proof. Obviously, for $k = 1$ and $k = 2$, the proposition is true.

If $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdot p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_i^{\alpha_i}$ divide $k! - 1$ or $k! + 1$, then $p_j > k \geq 3$, for $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, i\}$.

Let $\bar{n} = p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdots p_i$ and $p = \max_{1 \leq j \leq i} \{p_j\}$.

Obviously, $\bar{n} \geq 3$ because $p > k \geq 3$, $\bar{n}/k! - 1$ or $\bar{n}/k! + 1$.

For any $s \geq p$, $\bar{n}/s!$ and so, the triplets $(\bar{k}!)$, $(\bar{s}!)$ are not F -relatively prime.

Remark 1 i) Let $k < n$. If $(\bar{k}!)$, $(\bar{n}!)$ are linked, then $n - k = k! - k \pm 1$. If $2 < k_1 < n_1$, $(\bar{k}_1!)$ with $(\bar{n}_1!)$ are linked and $k_2 < n_2$, $(\bar{k}_2!)$ with $(\bar{n}_2!)$ are linked, then $k_1 < k_2 \Rightarrow n_1 - k_1 < n_2 - k_2$ and in view of the proposition 2, results $\text{card}M_{k_1 n_1} < \text{card}M_{k_2 n_2}$.

ii) There are twin prime numbers with the triplet $(\bar{n}!)$. For example 5 with 7 are from $(\bar{3}!)$.

Definition 14 Considering the canonical decomposition of natural numbers $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdot p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}$, we define $\bar{n} = \{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_r^{\alpha_r}\}$, $\mathcal{M} = \{\bar{n} | n \in \mathbb{N}^*\}$.

Definition 15 On \mathcal{M} we consider the relation of order \sqsubseteq defined by:

$$\{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_r^{\alpha_r}\} \sqsubseteq \{q_1^{\beta_1}, q_2^{\beta_2}, \dots, q_t^{\beta_t}\}$$

if and only if $\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r\} \subset \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_t\}$ and if $p_i = q_j$, then $\alpha_i \leq \beta_j$.

Remark 2 For any triplet $(\bar{n}!)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, we consider the sets:

$$A_n = \{k \in \mathbb{N}^* | \bar{k} \sqsubseteq \bar{n}!\}, A_n^* = \{k \in A_n | k \notin A_h \text{ for } h < n\}$$

$$B_n = \{k \in \mathbb{N}^* | \bar{k} \sqsubseteq \bar{n}! - 1\}, B_n^* = \{k \in B_n | k \notin B_h \text{ for } h < n\}$$

$$C_n = \{k \in \mathbb{N}^* | \bar{k} \sqsubseteq \bar{n}! + 1\}, C_n^* = \{k \in C_n | k \notin C_h \text{ for } h < n\}$$

$$M_n = \{k \in \mathbb{N}^* | \bar{k} \sqsubseteq \bar{n}! \text{ or } \bar{k} \sqsubseteq \bar{n}! - 1 \text{ or } \bar{k} \sqsubseteq \bar{n}! + 1\}$$

$$M_n^* = \{k \in M_n | k \notin M_h \text{ for } h < n\}.$$

It is obvious that:

$$A_n^* = S^{-1}(n), B_n^* = f_s^{-1}(n), C_n^* = f_d^{-1}(n), M_n^* = F^{-1}(n).$$

If $k \in A_n^*$, it is said that k has a factorial signature which is equivalent with the factorial signature of $n!$ (see [1]).

Let $k \in B_n^*$, $k = t_1^{r_1} \cdot t_2^{r_2} \cdots t_i^{r_i}$. Then $\{t_r\} \not\sqsubseteq \bar{n}!$ for $r = \bar{1}, i$ and for any $h < n$, there are $t_j^{r_j}$, $1 \leq j \leq i$, such that $\{t_j^{r_j}\} \not\sqsubseteq \bar{h}! - 1$.

Similarly, for $k \in C_n^*$: $\{t_r\} \not\sqsubseteq \bar{n}!$ for $r = \bar{1}, i$ and for any $h < n$, there are $t_j^{r_j}$, $1 \leq j \leq i$, such that $\{t_j^{r_j}\} \not\sqsubseteq \bar{h}! + 1$.

References

- [1] Bălăcenoiu I., *The Factorial Signature of Natural Numbers*, Smarandache Notions Journal, vol. 9, 1998, p. 70-78.
- [2] Bălăcenoiu I., Seleacu V., *Properties of the triplets \hat{p}* , Smarandache Notions Journal, vol. 8, 1997, p. 152-156.
- [3] Smarandache F., *A function in the Number Theory*, An. Univ. Timișoara, Ser. Șt. Mat., vol. XXVIII, fasc. 1, 1980, p. 79-88.

Current address:

Department of Mathematics, University of Craiova
13, Al. I. Cuza st., Craiova 1100, Romania